

Together,
there's
something
science
can do.

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[FDA publishes Complete Response Letters \(CRLs\)](#): On September 4, 2025, the FDA announced that it will publish CRLs – letters issued when an application for a drug or biologic cannot be approved in its current form due to identified deficiencies related to safety, efficacy, or manufacturing—“promptly” after issuing them and posted 89 previously unpublished CRLs from 2024 onward in its openFDA database. The agency said the change increases transparency, builds public trust in the fairness and scientific basis of its decisions, and [helps drug developers avoid mistakes that slow new treatments](#). The policy follows Executive Order 14303 on scientific transparency.

[Merck & Co scraps £1bn UK expansion](#) and [AstraZeneca pauses £200m investment](#): Merck (MSD in Europe) has cancelled its plans for a £1 billion Discovery Centre at Belgrove House in London and will vacate its labs at the London Bioscience Innovation Centre and the Francis Crick Institute by the end of 2025, cutting about 125 jobs. In the same week, AstraZeneca put its £200m investment in its Cambridge Research on pause, shifting investments to the US. Merck said the UK has become uncompetitive, pointing to underinvestment in life sciences and the undervaluation of innovative medicines. Merck will instead move its life sciences research to the United States, where it states that policies support higher pricing, faster approvals, and domestic R&D growth. More than \$9 billion in US R&D projects are underway.

[Eli Lilly launches TuneLab AI platform for drug discovery](#): Lilly unveiled TuneLab, an artificial intelligence system trained on its preclinical, safety, and experimental data, to help biotechnology companies accelerate early-stage research. By contributing their own data, partner companies help further refine the models. [Circle Pharma and insitro joined as the first collaborators](#).

[AbbVie extends Rinvoq exclusivity](#): AbbVie's shares hit a record high after the company settled all patent disputes over its immunology drug Rinvoq. The settlement delays generic competition in the United States until April 2037, four years later than expected. Rinvoq generated \$3.75 billion in sales in the first half of 2025, up 48% compared with the same period in 2024. The drug is approved for eight conditions, including ulcerative colitis and Crohn's disease, and AbbVie is testing it for new uses such as alopecia areata and vitiligo. Together with Skyrizi, which treats psoriasis and inflammatory bowel disease, Rinvoq is helping offset falling US sales of Humira, AbbVie's former top seller that lost patent protection in 2023.